

The Politics of Welfare Reform: Analyzing the Impact of the Two-Party System

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ABSTRACT

Welfare spending in the United States has dramatically increased over the past 50 years and as a consequence has provided greater opportunity for welfare dependency to occur. The two-party political climate has drawn support from different voter bases who benefit in different ways from contrasting welfare related policies resulting in welfare spending increasing despite different administrations over time. Meanwhile social factors remain prevalent and in conjunction with the growing welfare spending, partly caused by politics, has led to dependency. As politicians toe the party line, the prospect of bipartisanship shrinks along with the solutions to a constantly growing problem. Despite the influence of politics on the welfare state, its morals and ethics remain uncompromised making it even harder to amend.

Keywords: *Welfare state, dependency, two-party system, federal, expenditure, partisan*

1. INTRODUCTION

Political decisions have long shaped the structure and outcomes of welfare programs in the United States. Since its inception, the welfare state has evolved through key legislative acts, but questions remain about how these policies have fostered welfare dependency. Its roots can be traced back to when English-speaking colonialists brought aspects of the Poor Laws of 1601 into the New World helping those who were indigent through local taxation (Social Security Administration). Fast forward to a more modern age, social security and welfare benefits have been codified into law and the welfare state has expanded since President Roosevelt signed into law the Social Security Act of 1935 ushering into reality insurance against unemployment among other benefits. These programs were architected to raise the standard of living and protect against economic instability but like every other system, perhaps there exists some adverse effects that may be exploited. Some researchers have argued that the creation of a dependency culture has been fostered where there may be unintended long-term reliance or abuse of the framework intended to protect the destitute. The cycle of dependency refers to the

class of citizens who are overly reliant on government welfare through public welfare programs and are in essence trapped in a system that prolongs their dependence and poverty (Coe, 1982). Critics like Martin Anderson argue that welfare programs, though designed to alleviate poverty, have created 'a new caste of Americans... almost totally dependent on the State' (Anderson, 1978) which raises questions about the unintended consequences of such programs, including the possibility of fostering long-term reliance on government aid. (Anderson, 1978). Some of the largest welfare programs run today include food stamps and unemployment benefits; now known as the Supplement Assistance Nutrition Program, food stamps serve the purpose of providing food benefits to low-income families by supplementing their financial budget. The size of the benefit is based on a family's income and expenses and the budget of the program comes from a bipartisan congressional effort (CBPP, 2023). On the contrary, unemployment benefits are not provided federally but instead with each state running its own individual programs. These programs provide financial aid to those unemployed who also meet the requirements of local State law (Department of Labor). Previously established causes of welfare dependency include a variety of social and cultural factors but this paper aims to investigate whether politics has influenced welfare dependency. Today, the welfare state remains a thoroughly debated topic among politicians and continues to be a key debate point among political candidates standing for election.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Research into welfare dependency has identified several social, economic, and cultural factors contributing to long-term reliance on welfare programs. These factors can be grouped into four primary categories: parental influence, labor market conditions, substance abuse, and media portrayals. Parental influence is made clear by 3 main reasons; when parents participate in welfare, this may lower their offspring's distaste for welfare, essentially lowering the labor market opportunities for their offspring. Secondly, children learn from their parents' labor market experiences. As parents are less attached to work or career, children from welfare homes may be less aware of proper on-the-job behavior, may lack job search skills, and may have fewer informal job contacts. Finally, welfare participation costs may be lower for welfare children who will be familiar with the welfare system and can learn to 'cheat the system' (Antel, 1992). Likewise to the United States, a similar situation occurs in the Norwegian disability insurance system where analysis indicates that children whose parents received a lenient judge

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are more likely to apply for disability insurance and even report the same disability as their parent (Gordon B. Dahl, Andreas Ravndal Kostøl, Magne Mogstad, 2014). In both countries, the children are exposed to the practice since youth and more recent evidence that will be shown later implies that this has not changed since 2014. Despite a similarity among one of the key reasons for welfare dependency, the United States' social spending policy is distinct from many of the other democracies to which it is compared to. In comparison, it taxes less and spends less on social programs and the government heavily relies on private social benefits and services that employers provide for their employees rather than the government for everybody (Morgan, 2013). This would also mean that it is likely that those with higher pay will likely have better benefits whilst those with less pay may have worse benefits or even none. What can be taken away however is that the government's budgeting is not the root cause of welfare dependence since different budgets have yielded the same issue. On the other hand, some researchers argue that dependency culture is attributed to a lack of availability of jobs since those who are reliant on welfare, and are poor, often work as much as they are able to and to the limits family circumstances allow (Schiller, 1973). Whilst it is believed to be partly the case, there are other factors such as the previously determined parental factors that have long lasting effects on welfare dependency among others. When compared to the previously mentioned literature Monique De Haan, Ragnhild C. Schreiner (2018) finds that the causal effect of parental participation in welfare is considerably less than previously made estimates. The findings made then also suggest that there is important variety in the intergenerational transfer of welfare programs and that these differences are much larger for children of marginal welfare participants when compared to children of average welfare participants.

When looking beyond social factors, some researchers have made a case that alcohol addiction and substance abuse are also factors of welfare dependency since alcohol and drugs create functional impairments that significantly reduces a person's capacity to work. This in turn inhibits a person's ability to work one's way off welfare and to create independence away from the welfare state (Laura Schmidt et al. , 2002). This supports the notion that creating more viable job opportunities for the welfare class is essential in breaking the cycle. This is backed up by a phenomenon in the 'marriage market' where African American women are unable to find long term spouses due to cultural factors and therefore turn to welfare to support their children (Kimenyi, 1991). Kimenyi argues that policies aimed at reducing welfare dependency

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for this specific issue should focus on employment opportunities and drug treatment programs for African American men. The overall idea is that ultimately, employment opportunities are able to break the cycle by cutting the parental factors and by providing financial insurance to families to come out of welfare dependency.

One important thing to note is that the media's portrayal of welfare has been complicated over time. The way the media portrays sensitive topics serves as the eyes and ears of the public and therefore influences the narrative of how the public sees things. There have been positive portrayals of welfare programs, particularly during the 1980s and 1990s whilst earlier in the 1960s and 1970's the idea of dependency culture dominated the image of welfare programs (Misra, Moller, Karides, 2003). The portrayals are also asymmetric with the tendency to over portray African Americans as poor in the media, seen during the period 1993-1998, whereas those genuinely poor were underrepresented resulting in negative beliefs of the poor which in turn lead to a lack of support for welfare programs (Clawson, Trice, 2000). The takeaway is that dependency culture is a complex issue that stems from a myriad of factors with not one being more decisive than the other. There has already been a relative amount of literature about the cultural and social factors that have potentially caused welfare dependency but almost none covering political factors. This paper will aim to try and reason that there are political factors in place when analyzing welfare dependency.

Political implications on the welfare state:

The welfare state and politics has been intertwined since the politicization of welfare has led to a fluctuating landscape of support and resources for those in need. Politicians have long sought to use the welfare state as a campaign strategy, leveraging on welfare promises to garner voter support. This creates a cycle whereby politicians are incentivised to promise welfare expansions in order to attract votes and when elected, have a mandate to legislate over their promises resulting in expanding welfare. Often, as predicted by the rational choice theory, political motivations often prioritize short-term electoral gains over long-term welfare reform, which perpetuates dependency. When these programs are then introduced with loose requirements, it creates a gap allowing for welfare dependency without an incentive to escape.

State and Local Public Welfare Expenditures
(Percentage change in amounts, fiscal years 1977 to 2021 taken in 6 year intervals between 1977 and 2019 with 2021 data standalone)

Data compiled by the Urban Institute clearly indicate that public welfare expenditure has shot up significantly on the state level from 1977 to 2021. This rise in public welfare is also significantly larger than the rise in all other forms of public spending, totalling a 458% increase between that period. On the federal level there is a similar trend; in 2011, the Congressional Research Service outlined 83 overlapping federal welfare programs that combined, make up the largest single budget item in 2011, more than the nation spent on Medicare, Social Security or national defense in that year. The total amount spent on those 80 plus federal welfare programs amounted to roughly \$1.03 trillion and it is also important to note these programs are only means-tested welfare benefits and do not include other federal programs such as Medicare and Social Security (Jeff Sessions). Spending on the 10 largest of the 83 programs (which accounts for a significant portion of all federal welfare spending) has doubled in size as a percentage of the federal budget over the last 30 years. In inflation adjusted terms, the amount spent on these 10 programs has increased by 378% over that time (Jeff Sessions). As federal and state spending increases, it raises the question why it is increasing so much over time and how it is fueling dependency culture.

- **Why has spending increased?**

This significant increase in welfare spending raises questions about whether this expansion is driven by genuine need or by political strategies aimed at voter satisfaction. Politicians will weaponize the welfare state to garner support from voters, and upon being elected will be given the mandate and platform to enact and support such legislation. This is inline with the public choice theory where politicians are unfairly biased to serving their own self interest and act irrationally. Should they, upon being elected choose to turn back on election promises, they will now have to answer to the electorate and face potential backlash during reelection. This particular election promise however is mainly utilized by the Democrats who favor a larger welfare state. On the other hand, there is a history of Republicans weaponizing the tax code to appeal to those who want lower taxes and subsequently lead to a smaller and more restrictive public welfare state. However, what ends up happening is that when Republicans take control of the White House and Congress, there is a subsequent rise in the number and value of tax subsidies for private social welfare (Faricy, 2016).

In 2012 (election year), President Obama highlighted the importance of expanding welfare programs to combat poverty. Highlighted efforts included enhancing Earned Income Tax Credit and Child Tax Credit, supporting unemployment insurance benefits and food stamps whilst stating these initiatives helped keep many out of poverty (UCSB, 2012). Most significantly, he promised to and did remove work requirements out of welfare. All the previously mentioned policies actively enlarge the welfare state and make it easier for those in need to access federal level welfare, much in line with Democrat policy and what appeals to the lowest income voters. Similarly, the Republicans have also helped balloon welfare spending just disguised differently. In 2016, Mark Rubio offered tax credits for paid family leave whilst both Rubio and Jeb Bush proposed increasing tax subsidies for health insurance which would add to more than 80 social welfare programs consisting upwards of \$1 trillion.

Percent of registered voters in each income tier who are ... (Pew Research Center 2023)

This is inline with partisan support as shown in the table above indicating that strong Republican support lies in the middle income and upper middle income families who are likely to benefit from tax credit policies such as Rubio’s tax credit for paid family leave initiative. On the other hand strong Democrat support lies in the lower income and lower-middle income bracket who are likely to benefit from a larger public welfare state with looser employment regulations for claiming benefits.

- **Modern day effects:**

Even today, both parties still pursue similar policies that have led to increased welfare spending. Despite both major parties having ideological differences and their socio-economic policies differing in regulation to appeal to voters, the increase in welfare spending is alike. The American Rescue Plan spearheaded by President Biden increased Child Tax Credit to \$3000 per child and \$3600 for children under the age of 6 as well as increasing the claimable age limit to 17 (Matthews, 2023) was just one of the few policies supported by President Biden that saw an increase in welfare spending and loosening regulations for American families making it easier to claim. These policies are also inline with his party's predecessors. Similar policies may also exist on a state level with state executives pursuing an expansion of social welfare such as when Governor Kelly of Kansas tried to expand Medicaid and provide state

health coverage to another additional 150,000 people (Hanna, 2024). On the other side, Republican Governors may continue to appeal to voters by not raising state taxes, but instead use federal funding to expand Medicaid and increase welfare spending on the federal level as did by Governor Sandoval of Nevada (Families USA, 2017). Politicians on both sides of the aisle often maintain their parties stance on key economic objectives but what ends up happening is welfare spending increases one way or another. This relates to welfare dependency as larger welfare spending only fosters the cultural and social factors previously established to take effect and keep people on welfare assistance for longer. While political factors may not be directly believed to be in a casual relationship with welfare dependency, it could be concluded that a two party system has contributed to the expansion of welfare spending allowing other factors to Partisanship can often just be a disguise to help voters differentiate where the end result may end up being the same. As welfare spending increases, it creates a safety net that, while necessary, also risks diminishing the urgency for individuals to seek alternative means of financial stability, thus prolonging dependency. Essentially, political factors have indirectly contributed to welfare dependency by enlarging opportunities to do so or at the very least, not helped people get off welfare dependency.

- **The basis of a solution:**

Perhaps the only way to reduce welfare dependency politically is a bipartisan effort to reduce welfare spending and cut down on eligibility whilst providing more work opportunities without any form of financial assistance. In the short-run a drastic change like that will not be feasible but by lowering financial assistance over time, a key employment based plan can yield greater effects simultaneously. As many are reliant on the welfare system currently, it would take time to slowly disassemble the current system to ensure those who are reliant are not cut out of all support immediately. It should be stressed that such an effort must be bipartisan and without a certain class of voters being able to benefit more than others; the only way to do so would be to cut the government's role in welfare significantly and reduce the reliance from all classes whilst promoting alternatives. In the long run, the sustainable alternative would be to promote employment through employment based rights and employment based safety nets.

CONCLUSION:

As long as welfare spending continues to increase without corresponding efforts to reduce dependency, the number of people reliant on welfare will likely remain the same or grow. Politics at the very heart of it has contributed to that increase as politicians must appeal to the party line in order to win elections. Whether it is the Democrats or the Republicans in charge, welfare spending increases, just disguised differently or helping benefit a different class of people. Although partisan politics is contributing to greater welfare spending, its moral implications can not be considered unethical. Elections and voting are the heartbeat of a democracy and campaigning along party lines to increase welfare spending, if that is what the people vote for, is justifiable on the basis of the majority but the unchecked dependency it is helping keep alive is an unignorable side effect. Politics itself may not directly cause welfare dependency, but by continuously expanding welfare programs, it enables the social and cultural factors that perpetuate reliance on government support. Without direct efforts to address dependency and incentivize self-reliance, the cycle of welfare reliance will continue unchecked. Only through deliberate political and policy reform can this trend be reversed.

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